

ANNULAR SOLAR ECLIPSE

TOTAL SOLAR ECLIPSE

ECLIPSE
2023 THROUGH THE EYES OF NASA

**2024 Total Solar
eclipse**
THROUGH THE EYES OF NASA

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Join us for an annular solar eclipse on Saturday, October 14, 2023, and a total solar eclipse on Monday, April 8, 2024. Want to excite and engage learners? Explore Eclipse Resources: solarsystem.nasa.gov/eclipses/resources

When watching a partial, annular, or total solar eclipse directly with your eyes, you must look through safe solar viewing glasses (“eclipse glasses”) or other safe solar filters at all times. Learn more about eclipse safety: go.nasa.gov/EclipseEyeSafety

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